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Research Article

**A STUDY ON THE OCCURRENCE OF THE INFECTION OF
GIARDIASIS**¹Dr Muhammad Jahanzaib, ²Dr Muhammad Sajid Qasim, ³Dr Muhammad Ummail Abbas
¹Mayo Hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

Objectives: The aim of this research work was to find out the rate of occurrence of giardia lamblia in the children as well as adults and male & female members of our population of various social and economic classes in the city of Lahore, Pakistan.

Methodology: There were total five and ten participants in this research work. These patients were visiting the primary health care centers. The microscopic examination of the samples of stools carried out for every patient with the help of the procedure of formalin ethylacetate concentration. All the patients entered necessary information in the questionnaire. The study of the causative factor of this complication also carried out.

Results: The total occurrence rate of this infection was 29.60%. The prevalence rate for children was 78.0%, for adults 19.30%, for females 57.30% and for males it was 22.60%. In the total population of this research work, 82.40% patients were adults and 17.60% patients were children, 79.80% population of this research work was males and there were total 20.20% patients of this work were females. The social and economic condition of the patients was not an important feature for the occurrence of the infection of giardiasis, but the significant causative and contributory factors were age and gender of the patient.

Conclusion: The main causative factors for the wide spreading of this infection of giardiasis is water, hygiene of population & sanitation system. This research work has much worth for the workers in the health care field, engineers in the field of sanitation and various policies in the health care field.

Keywords: Giardia, Prevalence, Occurrence, Formalin Ethyl Acetate, Sanitation, Healthcare, Infection, Giardiasis.

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the most leading contributory reason of diarrhea among children is the infection of giardia lamblia. The research works on the onset of development of the diseases have displayed that the diarrhea of parasite among children is mainly because of the infection of giardia lamblia whereas among adults it is the outcome of the infection of the entamobia histolytica, especially in the regions where the sources of fresh water and vegetable have contaminations due to the mixing of the materials from sewage and in the food stuff purchased vendors working in streets [1].

Poor sanitation and poor water supplies have remained major reasons for the spread of this infection among various countries of work particularly those which are under development. This transverse research work states that the occurrence of the infection of giardia lamblia among our common general public and the association of this disease with the income of the family, the level of qualification of the patients and sex and age of the persons.

METHODOLOGY:

There were total 510 participants of this transverse research work. These patients were visiting the primary health care centers in Lahore, Pakistan, for different medical as well as surgical sessions. The collection of the stool samples carried out from every patient. Every patient or the escort of the children filled our designed questionnaire to provide the required information. Microscopic outcome of cysts

and/or trophozoites available in the sample of stool was in use for the grading of patients as positive or as negative with the utilization of the method of formalin ethyl acetate concentration. The selection of the primary health care centers was depending upon the geographical location of the region, social and economic condition of the population and living status of the people in the community.

Total 170 samples of stools collection carried out from each of 3 primary health care centers in different parts of the city describing the low social and economic condition in the east regions of the city, medium level social and economic condition in the middle regions of the city and highest social and economic condition was present in the west part of the city among deferent age groups and genders.

RESULTS:

The collection of total 510 samples of stools carried out in this research work from 3 different centers of primary health care, choice depending upon the social and economic condition and distribution of the people carried out according to geographical regions with the representation of the less level of income, medium level of income and high level of income. The stratification of the samples carried out in accordance with sex and age of the persons. In the total population of this research work, 82.40% patients were adults and 17.60% patients were children, 79.80% population of this research work was males and there were total 20.20% patients of this work were females as well-elaborated in Table-1.

Table-I : The Distribution of the Sample According to Sex and Age

Age	Number		Total	Percent (%)
	males	females		
Children*	55.0	35.0	90.0	17.60
Adult	352.0	68.0	420.0	82.40
Total	407.0	103.0	510.0	-
Percent (%)	79.8	20.2	-	100.00

Children were < 14 years.

The overall rate of prevalence of the positive infection of giardia lamblia detected microscopically was 29.60%. There were total one hundred and fifty-

one patients suffering from this very infection among total five hundred and ten patients as elaborated in Table-2.

Table-II : Prevalence Rate of Giardia Lamblia

Age	No	Positive Cases	Positive Percent
Children	90.0	70.0	78.00
Adult	420.0	81.0	19.30
Total	510.0	151.0	29.60

p-value <0.05

The occurrence rate of this infection in children was 78.0% and in adults it was 19.30%. This showed that the occurrence rate of this infection of giardia lamblia among the children was very high in comparison with the adult patients as presented in Table-2. Another vital causative factor in the rate of occurrence of giardia lamblia among the studied samples was the

gender of the patients. The prevalence rate of this infection in females was 57.0% and rate of this infection in males was 22.60%. Table-3 fully describes that the infection of giardia lamblia in very high among females in comparison with the male participant of the research work.

Table-III : Prevalence rate of Giardia Lamblia according to gender

Gender	Number	Positive cases	% positive
Male	407.0	92.0	22.60
Female	103.0	59.0	57.30
Total	510.0	151.0	29.60

p-value <0.05

DISCUSSION:

This was the very first research work on the onset and development as well as associated risk factors of the infection of giardia in the city of Lahore on this particular topic. Majority of the research reports of the infection of Giardiasis have assessed either a definite group of population of the data depending upon the cases of the hospital. The overall rate of occurrence of the infection of giardiasis among the people of Lahore was 29.60% as presented in this current research work. The amounts of the collected samples from all 3 centers of primary health care were one hundred and seventy from each center. This collection amount of the samples was satisfactory for fulfilling the size of the study population.

There was not any important disparity available in the rate of occurrence in all 3 centers of primary health care (29.30%, 28.60%, and 30.10%) which displays that there is no role of the social and economic factor on the occurrence of this disease. These findings are consistent with the outcomes of the research work conducted in India [2] and Turkey [3]. Opposite results were available in the conclusion of a research work conducted in region of Abha located in Saudi Arabia examining the impact of social and economic features of the occurrence of the infection of giardiasis. One research work concluded that there was no disparity between different social

and economic classes [4] whereas one other research stated a very incidence of this infection among persons from low social & economic condition [5].

There was a report from non-urban Lesotho which is a small country in Africa that the utilization of the small amount of water due to low supply of water was the main causative factor behind the high prevalence of the infection of giardiasis, it is very much vital in comparison with the contaminated water for drinking and the deficiency of latrines [6]. The results of that work showed that the amount of the water but not the water quality utilized for domestic or personal hygiene in the countries which are under development appears to play an important role in the increase of this infection [7-8].

The distribution of the age of patients suffering from the disease of giardiasis displayed that very high rate of the infection was present among children since they use [9] eatables haphazardly and they have low level of immunity to the parasite of disease in comparison with the adults who have exposure to those parasites in their childhood days [10]. There was very high occurrence of this infection among females in comparison with the male patients (57.30% & 22.60%, respectively). This can happen because of the continuous contact with the water for washing purposes, child minding or clearance of

washrooms and latrines and with the children available with a high rate of infection of this disease [11].

The findings of this research work gave the sign of the patterns and occurrence of the infection of giardiasis in the mix population of the city of Lahore. There are serious impacts of the different levels of the sanitation system in different areas of city [12]. The infection of the intestines due to parasites especially infection of giardiasis appears to be serious problem of the health of public. Deficiency of the awareness about the infection of giardiasis among our population particularly mothers support to the transmission of disease among children [13].

CONCLUSION:

There are many prompting factors for the spread of the infection of giardiasis is water, hygiene of population & sanitation system. There is a need of focused attention on the education of the public for health and better supply of water.

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